

Effect of Plant Mediated Synthesis on Structural, Electrical, Optical and Anti-bacterial Studies of Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles

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Plant mediated synthesis has been suggested as easy, low cost and eco- friendly method [1]. Zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO 1 , ZnO 2 , ZnO 3) were synthesized by plant mediated synthesis using the medicinal plants, *Andrographis paniculata*, *Phyllanthus niruri* and *Carica papaya*. The hexagonal wurtzite structure of all the three ZnO NPs was confirmed by XRD. SEM analysis shows variations in morphology for ZnO 1, ZnO 2 and ZnO 3. The alterations in absorption and bandgap and dielectric constant are due to the reaction rate of phytochemicals during synthesis besides size effects. All the three nanoparticles produce high excitonic UV emission in addition to blue light emission. Two gram positive bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* and two gram negative bacteria such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli* were taken for antibacterial study. The order of antibacterial activity for *S.aureus* is ZnO 1 > ZnO 3 > ZnO 2 and for *B.subtilis* is ZnO 3 > ZnO 1 > ZnO 2. The activity of ZnO 3 is 10% less than ZnO 1 and ZnO 2 for *P.aeruginosa* and ZnO 1 and ZnO 3 is 5% less than ZnO 2 for *E.coli*. The very high surface to volume ratio as well as the release of reactive oxygen species of ZnO nanoparticles gives rise to high toxicity to micro organisms thereby leading to large zone of inhibition [2, 3].

References

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2. Balaram Das et al, Arabian journal of chemistry,10(2017), 862-876.
3. Amna Sirelkhatim et al, Nano-micro letters, 7(2015), 219-242.